

IN VITRO EVALUATION OF BIOAGENTS AND ESSENTIAL OILS AGAINST *Sphaceloma rosarum*

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MS Received: 26.05.2024; MS Revised:30.06.2024; MS Accepted:01.07.2024)

MS 3222

(RESEARCH PAPER IN PLANT PATHOLOGY,)

Abstract

Among the bioagents and essential oil evaluated in in vitro against *Sphaceloma rosarum* bioagent *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Trichoderma asperellum* and *Paecilomyces lilacinus* recorded significantly highest inhibitions of mycelium viz., 71.48, 55.37 and 49.42 per cent, respectively. Essential oils at 2500 ppm concentration, maximum mycelial inhibition of 94.44 percent was seen with Clove oil (*Syzygium aromaticum*) followed by Lemon oil (*Citrus limonum*) 88.19 per cent and rose oil (*Rosa damascene*) 77.12 per cent, while at 3000 ppm concentration, Clove and Lemon (*Syzygium aromaticum* and *Citrus limonum*) showed 94.44 per cent growth inhibition of *Sphaceloma rosarum*. The next effective essential oils in order of growth inhibition were *Cymbopogon nardus* 88.27 per cent, Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) 87.23 per cent and Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*).

Keywords: *Sphaceloma rosarum*, Bioagent, Rose, *Trichoderma*

Introduction

Rose is one of the most important ornamental/horticultural crops grown throughout the world (Debener *et al.*, 2004). In India, rose constitutes 45 per cent share of total world trade in floriculture production. Owing to all these qualities, rose was rightly referred to as the 'Queen of Flowers' firstly by a Greek poetess in her poem 'Ode to the rose' (Muhammad *et al.*, 1996). The area under rose cultivation in India in the year 2015 - 2016 was 29,410 ha. The production of roses in the corresponding year was 1,13,190 MT for loose flowers and about 1,88,760 MT for cut flowers (Anonymous, 2016 a). During the year 2015 - 16, the net area under rose cultivation in Maharashtra was 1,560 ha producing 2880 MT of loose flowers and 27,770 MT of cutflowers (Anonymous, 2016 b). The important rose crop producing districts of Maharashtra are Aurangabad, Jalna, Nanded, Parbhani, Pune, Nashik, Ahmednagar, Kolhapur and Satara. Rose has numerous illnesses brought on by germs, viruses, and fungi. The bacterial diseases crown gall (*Agrobacterium tumefaciens*), viral diseases rose mosaic (PNRSV), die-back (*Diplodia rosarum*), black spot (*Diplocarpon rosae*), botrytis blight (*Botrytis cinera*), cankers (*Coniothyrium fuckelli*), powdery mildew (*Sphaeretheca pannosa*), downy mildew (*Pernospora sparsa*), rust (*Phragmidis disciflora*), die-back (*Diplodia rosarum*), black spot (*Diplocarpon rosae*), illnesses caused by bacteria, such as crown gall (*Agrobacterium tumefaciens*), cankers (*Coniothyrium fuckelli*), rose mosaic (PNRSV), rose rosette (*Rose rosette virus*), and botrytis blight (*Botrytis cinera*) Pal, (1966) and Sinha, (2017). *Sphaceloma rosarum* is the cause of anthracnose, one of the most prevalent illnesses affecting roses. Italy provided the first account of anthracnose on roses in 1881. It was first

documented on wild roses in the United States in 1898. According to Ong (2015), the disease known by the common name anthracnose is brought on by a group of fungi that induce comparable symptoms in a variety of host plants, including numerous types of trees and shrubs. The fungus *Sphaceloma rosarum* causes anthracnose on roses, which manifests as a range of symptoms including patches on the leaves of affected plants. It could result in significant defoliation if left untreated. There were tiny reddish-purple stains on the veins of the leaves. Eventually, the spots got black, and the border was surrounded by a thin brown margin. Unlike the feathery margins of black dots, the edges of leaf spots were defined and smooth. Shot-hole lesions were left behind when the leaf spots' centers became gray and eventually fell out. The leaves prematurely dropped, wilted, and became yellow. *In vitro* evaluation of bioagents and essential oil provides preliminary information regarding its efficacy against a pathogen within a shortest period of time and therefore, serves a guide for further field testing hence the present investigation was undertaken to screen a range of bio control agents and essential oil, including new bioagents and essential oil for their ability to inhibit the mycelia growth of *in vitro*.

Material And Methods

An experiment was conducted during 2021 at Department of Plant Pathology, VNMKV, Parbhani. To find out the effective bioagents and essential oil against *Sphaceloma rosarum* *in vitro*. The experiment was designed Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with bioagents three replication and eight treatments and essential oil nine treatments respectively.

Table 1 A. In vitro evaluation of bio control agents against *Sphaceloma rosarum*

Treatment	Bioagent
T1	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>
T2	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>
T3	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>
T4	<i>Verticillium lecanii</i>
T5	<i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i>
T6	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>
T7	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
T8	Control

The dual culture technique was used to test the antifungal activity of bioagents. The different bioagents were tested against *Sphaceloma rosarum*. The pathogen and bioagents were grown on different media for a week at 25 ± 2°C. 5mm disc of the target fungi cut from the periphery was transferred to the Petri dish previously poured with sterilized potato dextrose agar media. Bioagents were transferred

aseptically in the same plate at opposite end and incubated at room temperature with alternate light and darkness for 7 days and observed periodically. Control plates were also maintained without bioagents. Mycelial growth of test pathogen was tested after 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours Per cent inhibition over control was calculated by using formula

$$R = \{(C - T) / C\} \times 100$$

Table 1 B. *In vitro* evaluation of against essential oils

Treatment	Essential Oils	Rate of Application
T1	Lemon (<i>Citrus limonum</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T2	Eucalyptus (<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T3	Rose (<i>Rosa damascena</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T4	Ginger (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T5	Clove (<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T6	Citronella (<i>Cymbopogon nardus</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T7	Cardamom (<i>Elettaria ardamomum</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T8	Lavender (<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>)	2500 ppm , 3000 ppm
T9	Control	

Observations on radial mycelial growth/colony diameter were recorded at 24 hours interval and continued till the untreated control plates were fully covered with mycelial growth of the test fungus. Per cent mycelial growth inhibition of the test pathogen over untreated control was calculated by applying the formula:

$$R = \{(C - T) / C\} \times 100$$

Result And Discussion

In-vitro evaluation of bioagents/antagonists

Results revealed that all the bioagents evaluated exhibited fungistatic/antifungal activity against *Sphaceloma rosarum* and

significantly inhibited its growth over untreated control. The antagonistic activity of fungal bioagents against *Sphaceloma rosarum* revealed that all the eight antagonists caused significant inhibition of mycelial growth of the test fungus (Table 2. Plate 1). However, maximum inhibition of mycelial growth was obtained with *T. harzianum* (71.48%), with least colony diameter of 25.66 mm, which was significantly superior over all the treatments. This was followed by *Trichoderma asperellum* (55.37%) and *Paecilomyces lilacinus* (49.42%) with mycelial growth reductions of 40.15 mm and 45.51 mm, respectively.

Table 2. *In vitro* efficacy of different bioagents against *Sphaceloma rosarum*

Tr. No.	Treatments	Colony Diameter *(mm)	Per cent Inhibition #
T1	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	40.15	55.37 (48.08)
T2	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	25.66	71.48 (57.72)
T3	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	45.79	49.11 (44.49)
T4	<i>Verticillium lecanii</i>	50.44	43.95 (41.52)
T5	<i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i>	45.51	49.42 (44.66)
T6	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	57.3	36.33 (37.06)
T7	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	58.6	34.88 (36.19)
T8	Control	90.00	00.00 (00.00)
S. E. (m) ±		0.540	0.656
C.D (P = 0.01)		1.633	1.984

*Mean of three replications, Dia.=Diameter,

#Figures in parenthesis are arc sine transformed value

These were followed by *Metarhizium anisopliae* (colony diameter 45.79 mm and inhibition: 49.11%) and *Verticillium lecanii* (colony diameter: 50.44 mm and inhibition: 43.95%). The bacterial antagonists *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *B. subtilis* were found to cause significant inhibition of mycelial growth of the test fungus (*S. rosarum*) with 57.3 mm and 58.6 mm linear mycelial growth and (36.33%) and (34.88%) mycelial inhibition, respectively. However, least inhibition of mycelial growth was found with *B. subtilis* (34.88%). The present results were in conformity with Stack *et al.*, (1986) who reported that *T. harzianum* was observed as the most effective than other bioagents with per cent inhibition of (53.33%) (46.90) followed by *T. viride* with 52.32% (46.32). *Gliocladium* spp. was the least effective for control with 42.18 per cent (39.91) inhibition. Kulkarni (2019) reported that *Trichoderma harzianum* gave highest growth inhibition (64.38%), followed by *Gliocladium virens* (58.47%), *T. koningii* (54.37%) and *T. viride* (50.46%). The least growth inhibition of the fungus was observed in *Bacillus subtilis* (35.44%) and *Pseudomonas fluorescens*.

Plate 1 Effect of Bioagents against *Sphaceloma rosarum*

T₁- *Trichoderma asparallum*

T₂- *Trichoderma harzianum*

T₃- *Metarhizium anisopliae*

T₄- *Verticillium lecanii*

T₅- *Paecilomyces lilacinus*

T₆- *Pseudomonas fluorescens*

T₇- *Bacillus subtilis*

T₈- Control

Table 3 *In vitro* efficacy of essential oils against *S. rosarum*

Tr.No	Treatment	Colony Dia *(mm)		Per cent Inhibition #	
		2500 ppm	3000 ppm	2500 ppm	3000 ppm
T1	Lemon oil	10.62	5.00	88.19 (69.90)	94.44 (76.36)
T2	Eucalyptus oil	50.33	45.55	44.07 (41.59)	49.38 (44.64)
T3	Rose oil	20.59	10.88	77.12 (61.42)	87.91 (69.65)
T4	Ginger oil	28.53	18.33	68.3 (55.73)	79.63 (63.17)
T5	Clove oil	5.00	5.00	94.44 (76.36)	94.44 (76.36)
T6	Citronella oil	35.55	10.54	60.5 (51.06)	88.27 (69.97)
T7	Cardamom oil	90.00	90.00	-	-
T8	Lavender oil	50.00	11.41	43.83 (41.45)	87.23 (69.06)
T9	Control	90.00	90.00	-	-
SE(m) ±		0.411	0.430	0.471	0.430
C.D (P=0.01)		1.411	1.289	1.411	1.289

*Mean of three replications, Dia.=Diameter,

#Figures in parenthesis are arc sine transformed value

Results (Table 3 and Plate 2) revealed that all the tested essential oils (each at 2500, 3000 ppm) exhibited a wide range of radial mycelial growth of *Sphaceloma rosarum* over untreated control (90.00 mm) and mycelial growth found to decrease with increase in the concentrations of the essential oils tested.

At 2500 ppm, the growth of *Sphaceloma rosarum* exhibited radial mycelial growth from 5.00 mm (Clove) to 90.00 mm (Cardamom oil), as against 90.00 mm in untreated control. However, Clove oil was found best with least mycelial growth (5.00 mm), followed by Lemon oil (10.62 mm). This was followed by Rose oil (20.59 mm), Ginger oil (28.53 mm), Citronella oil (35.55 mm), Lavender oil (50.00 mm) and Eucalyptus oil (50.33 mm). Amongst all the essential oils, Cardamom oil was found comparatively less effective with maximum mycelial growth of 90.00 mm. At 3000 ppm, the growth of *Sphaceloma rosarum* exhibited radial mycelial growth from 5.00 mm (Lemon oil and Clove oil) to 90.00 mm (Cardamom oil), as against 90.00 mm in untreated control. However, Lemon oil and Clove oil were found best with least mycelial growth (5.00 mm), followed by Citronella oil (10.54 mm). This was followed by Rose oil (10.88 mm), Lavender oil (11.41 mm), Ginger oil (18.33 mm) and Eucalyptus oil (42.55 mm). Amongst all the essential oils, Cardamom oil was found comparatively less effective with maximum mycelial growth of 90.00 mm. Results (Table 3 and Plate 2) revealed that all eight essential oils tested (each @ 2500, 3000 ppm) significantly inhibited mycelial growth of *Sphaceloma rosarum* over untreated control. Further, the percentage of mycelial growth inhibition increased with increase in concentrations of the fungicides tested. At 2500 ppm, the mycelial growth inhibition of *Sphaceloma rosarum* ranged from (0.00%) (Cardamom oil) to (94.44%) (Clove oil). However, Clove oil was found best which inhibited (94.44%) mycelial growth of the pathogen, followed by Lemon oil (88.19%). This was followed by Rose oil (77.12%), Ginger oil (68.3%), Citronella oil (60.5%), Eucalyptus oil (44.07%) and Lavender oil (43.83%). Amongst all the essential oils, Cardamom oil was found comparatively less effective with maximum mycelial inhibition of (16.10%). At 3000 ppm, the mycelial growth inhibition of *Sphaceloma rosarum* ranged from (94.44%) (Clove oil and Lemon oil) to (0.00%) (Cardamom oil). However, Clove oil and Lemon oil were found best with least mycelial growth (94.44 %) followed by Citronella oil (88.27%). This was followed by Rose oil (87.91%), Lavender oil (87.23 mm), Ginger oil (79.63%), Eucalyptus oil (49.38%). Amongst all the essential oils, Cardamom oil was found comparatively less effective with maximum mycelial inhibition of (0.00%). Thus, all the essential oil tested were found effective against *Sphaceloma rosarum* and significantly inhibited its mycelial growth over untreated control. The present results were in conformity with Wang *et al.*, (2019) reported that clove oil was seen to be the most active inhibitor against *C. gloeosporioides* tested in vitro and in vivo by different treatments, and its fungitoxic activities may be attributed to the destruction of the cell wall and cell membrane, and the leakage

of intracellular constituents. Daniele *et al.*, (2020) reported that *in vitro* antifungal activities of eight essential oils against *C. gloeosporioides* and evaluated the mycelial growth and sporulation on PDA medium with different concentrations of the emulsified essential oils. Our results demonstrated that clove, citronella and mint essential oils can suppress *C. gloeosporioides* development *in vitro* and that, at 0.25%, these essential oils can either protect pepper seeds from increased incidence of anthracnose in greenhouse conditions.

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T₁- Lemon
T₂- Eucalyptus
T₃- Rose
T₄- Ginger
T₅- Clove

T₆- Citronella
T₇- Cardamom
T₈- Lavender
T₉- Control

Plate 2 Effect of Essential oils against *Sphaceloma rosarum*